

Supplementary Material: Designing a zero-order energy transition model: a guide for creating a Starter Data Kit

Title	Designing a zero-order energy transition model: how to create a new Starter Data Kit
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This document contains instructions on how to create a starter kit, with information on the following steps:

- Data collection & preparation
- Model & scenario creation
- Generation of article and figures
- Creation of Zenodo repository
- Upload of article pre-print

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1. Base Data

The Base Data Collection Files for each country are pre-filled with data that will remain the same for all countries in the region. These data will likely need to be updated in the future. Below is a summary of where the base data for each region were sourced from, and further detail can be found in the pre-print articles.

Depreciation Method, Discount Rate and Year Split

Defaults values were used for these parameters: Depreciation Method = 1; Discount Rate = 0.1; Year Split = 1/96 for all 96 time slices so that they are of equal length.

Technology Costs – Africa

Costs of refinery and transmission and distribution technologies from TEMBA report. Costs for renewables taken from IRENA (2021) Planning & Prospects for Renewable Power: Eastern & Southern Africa – this provides 5-yearly projected costs to 2040, with linear change assumed between datapoints and costs assumed constant after 2040. The costs of offshore wind were taken from IRENA (2019) The Future of Wind. Costs for fossil power plants were taken from IRENA (2018) Planning & Prospects for Renewable Power: West Africa (because the gas and coal costs were deemed less realistic in the 2021 report). Generic costs of transport and heating technologies were taken from Terpilowski Gill (2020) Decarbonising the Laotian Energy System. The costs of energy efficiency technologies were estimated based on the costs of coal power plants – see [here](#). Costs of stoves were taken from Okolo O, Teng H. (2017) Analysing Nigeria’s Energy system in light of the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals. Costs of renewables with storage were estimated by combining the standard cost from the IRENA report with an estimated storage cost based on the NREL 2020 Annual Technology Baseline – see [here](#). The oil price was estimated based on the forecast in U.S. EIA. (2020) Assumptions to the Annual Energy Outlook 2020: International Energy Module, which was extended to 2070 [here](#). The price was increased by 10% for imported oil and the prices of imported HFO and LFO were estimated by calculating 80% and 133% of the domestic oil price respectively, as done in TEMBA. Prices of other fuels were taken from IRENA (2018) Planning and Prospects for Renewable Power: West Africa. More detail on costs can be found in the Base Data Preparation file.

Technology Costs – Developing Asia

Costs of refinery technologies were taken from the TEMBA report. Costs of power plants were mostly taken from the IRENA ASEAN ReMap Report – the cost given by IRENA for ‘Oil’ was used for LFO plants, and then this was increased by 12% to estimate costs for HFO plants based on the relationship between LFO and HFO technology costs in the IRENA report used for Africa. The same was done for gas, where the IRENA ASEAN ReMap value for gas was used for CCGTs and reduced by 21% to estimate OCGT costs. The costs of renewables were estimated from IRENA (2020) Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2019, using the average values for all Asian countries considered, and the IRENA ASEAN ReMap report, with the cost reduction trends from the report used for Africa applied. Costs of transmission and distribution were estimated based on this [ERIA report](#). Generic costs of transport and heating technologies were taken from Terpilowski Gill (2020) Decarbonising the Laotian Energy System. The costs of energy efficiency technologies were estimated based on the

costs of coal power plants – see [here](#). Costs of stoves were estimated from the IRENA ASEAN REmap Report and IRENA (2017) Biogas for Domestic Cooking. Costs of renewables with storage were estimated by combining the standard cost from the IRENA reports with an estimated storage cost based on the NREL 2020 Annual Technology Baseline – see [here](#). Fuel prices were taken from the APEC 7th Annual Energy Outlook. The international biomass price was estimated from a report by [Argus Media](#) and the domestic biomass price was estimated from an [ERIA report](#). More detail on costs can be found in the Base Data Preparation file.

Technology Costs – South America

Costs of refinery technologies were taken from the TEMBA report. Costs of transmission and distribution technologies from SAMBA dataset. Costs for renewables taken from SAMBA dataset from 2013 to 2058 – linear change between data points (2013 and 2058). Then constant from 2058 until the end. The cost of CSP with Storage was estimated from the cost of CSP without storage (from SAMBA Dataset) - it was applied a percentage increase taken from IRENA ACEC (Africa Clean Energy Corridor). The cost of Medium Hydropower plants (10-100MW) and Solar PV (Distributed with Storage) were taken from IRENA ACEC Planning Report, as there were no data available in SAMBA. The costs of Off-grid Hydropower plants were assumed to be the same as Small Hydropower Plants. Costs for fossil power plants were taken from SAMBA Dataset from 2013 and 2058, then constant from 2058 until the end. The cost of Coal Power Plant was assumed to be double the capital cost of Gas Power Plant (CCGT). Therefore, the coal price from SAMBA Dataset was reduced to be in line with more recent reports. The cost of Light Fuel Oil Power Plant was taken from IRENA (2018) Planning & Prospects for Renewable Power: West Africa as no data were available in SAMBA Dataset. Generic costs of transport and heating technologies were taken from Terpilowski Gill (2020) Decarbonising the Laotian Energy System. The costs of energy efficiency technologies were estimated based on the costs of coal power plants – see [here](#). Costs of stoves were taken from Okolo O, Teng H. (2017) Analysing Nigeria's Energy system in light of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. Costs of renewables with storage were estimated by combining the standard cost from the IRENA report with an estimated storage cost based on the NREL 2020 Annual Technology Baseline – see [here](#). The oil price was estimated based on the forecast in U.S. EIA. (2020) Assumptions to the Annual Energy Outlook 2020: International Energy Module, which was extended to 2070 [here](#). The price was increased by 10% for imported oil and the prices of imported HFO and LFO were estimated by calculating 80% and 133% of the domestic oil price respectively, as done in TEMBA. Price of Biomass Extraction was taken from Ricardo Energy & Environment – Global Biomass Markets (see [here](#)). Price of Coal Extraction were taken from SAMBA Dataset, assuming a linear growth between data points, growth rate between 2020-2030 is continued to 2040 then price assumed constant to 2071. Prices of Natural Gas Extraction were taken from SAMBA Dataset – average value was used if no country specific data were available and calculated (see [here](#)). More detail on costs can be found in the Base Data Preparation file.

Input & Output Activity Ratios

Country-specific efficiencies for power transmission and distribution were used (detailed in sections 2-5). For Africa, efficiencies of power plants were taken from IRENA (2018) Planning and Prospects for Renewable Power: West Africa and efficiencies of stoves were taken from the Okolo & Teng report used for stove costs. For Asia, efficiencies of power plants and stoves were taken from the IRENA ASEAN REmap report. For South America. Efficiencies of transport and heating technologies in all countries were taken from Terpilowski Gill (2020) Decarbonising the Laotian Energy System.

Capacity to Activity Unit, Operational Life & Capacity Factors

Default values were used for Capacity-to-Activity unit. Operational lives were taken from the same reports used for technology costs in each region. Capacity factors for fossil, biomass & nuclear power plants were also taken from those reports. Country-specific capacity factors for wind, solar and hydropower technologies were used, sourced from the PLEXOS dataset (based on Renewables Ninja) and global NREL datasets where necessary (detailed in sections 2-5).

Emissions Factors

Emissions factors were sourced from IPCC (2006) Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Volume 2: Energy, Table 1.3.

All other data are country-specific and detailed in sections 2-5 for each region.

2. Data Preparation for Africa

Step 1

Create a copy of the Africa Base Data Collection File (without opening the file) for your country in the same Data Preparation and Manipulation folder. Name the file: **New *countryname* Data Collection**. Open the file (in desktop app) and give it a little time. Click do not update links when the file loads.

Select the country in Tab 1. Model Initiation. Give it a little time to update everything.

Step 2 - Power transmission and distribution output activity ratios

Copy the output activity ratio rows for power transmission and distribution from the **TEMBA_21_10_Refer** dataset (in the SharePoint Data Preparation & Manipulation folder [here](#)) to the rows in the **3.3 Output Activity Ratios tab**. In TEMBA, the codes for power transmission and distribution technologies are **XXELOOT00X** and **XXELOOTDTX** respectively, where XX is the country code, which can be found [here](#) if needed.

- In the TEMBA Output Activity Ratios tab, copy the entire row for XXELOOT00X from column D to column BG and paste into row 41 of tab 3.3 Output Activity Ratios, starting in column F
- In the TEMBA Output Activity Ratios tab, copy the entire row for XXELOOTDTX from column D to column BG and paste into row 42 of tab 3.2 Output Activity Ratios, starting in column F

Step 3 - PV, onshore & offshore wind and hydro capacity factors

This is automated. Check data for your country is inserted in the Raw PV/Onshore Wind/Hydro/Offshore Wind CFs tabs (not the (auto) tabs) and that output capacity factors for these technologies are in the output capacity factors tab.

Step 4 - Off-grid capacity

Copy and paste the Cumulative/Additions Label for off-grid hydropower and off-grid solar PV for the country from the IRENA Installed Capacities data (in SharePoint Data Preparation & Manipulation folder [here](#)) into the Off-Grid Capacity tab. Note: if the IRENA file has the country but not the relevant off-grid technologies, assume the values are zero and you don't need to do anything.

- In the IRENA datasheet, ensure the 'Type' column (column AC) is filtered to '**off-grid**'
- Filter to your **country** in the 'IRENA Menu' column (column A)
- In the '**Sub-technology**' column, filter to Solar Photovoltaic

- Order by Years and then copy the 'Cumulative/Additions Label' column (column AL) into tab **3.7 Off-Grid Capacity**, cells C5-C24 – if there is no data for a year then put 0, ensure the years match up with the years in column A
- Repeat the process but filtering out for Renewable Hydropower as the sub-technology, copying the Cumulative/Additions Label column into cells B5-B24 in the tab 3.7 Off-Grid Capacity

Check that the residual capacity rows for PWR SOL002 and PWRHYD004 (rows 920 and 1085) are updated in the **3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab**.

If not in the IRENA list, you can use the TEMBA file, go to the residual capacity tab:

- Copy the rows in the residual capacity tab for XXSOV1F01X and XXSOV2F01X from cell B to cell BE. If 0 in all years, you don't need to do anything,
- Paste those rows into tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab in rows 1065 and 1066 (PWR SOL002), starting in column I (to the right of the yellow cells).
- Ensure that the orange Residual Capacity row for PWR SOL002 (row 1085) is updated if you added values.
- We will exclude off-grid hydropower in this case since TEMBA does not include this technology.

Step 5 - On-grid residual capacity

This is automated. Check that on-grid residual capacity data for your country is in the 3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab. Focus on checking between rows 724-1197 as this is where the power plant technologies are (all begin with PWR).

The raw on-grid residual capacity data for your country can be found in a csv file [here](#) - check that there are no more than 11 power plants of each type in your country as this is the maximum number permitted by the spreadsheet. If there are more than 11 rows you can add extra rows manually and copy the extra data directly from the csv file.

A few manual adjustments are needed:

- For hydropower (rows 852-920), move any plants in the PWRHYD001 group to PWRHYD002 if they have capacity between 0.01-0.1GW, and to PWRHYD003 if less than 0.01GW (capacity is in column H). To move a plant, copy the entire row for that plant from column E to column AR and paste it in the corresponding cells for the technology group you are moving it to.
- For oil power plants (rows 985-1016), all residual capacity is automatically inserted as PWROHC001 (LFO plant), but you can do a quick Google search using the Power Plant name and move any plants to PWROHC002 (HFO gas turbine) using the method above if needed. If it is unclear or you can't find anything, leave the plant where it is.
- The same should be done for gas power plants (rows 921-952), moving plants from PWRNGS001 (CCGT) to PWRNGS002 (OCGT) if you can find out that the plant is an OCGT. If it is unclear or you can't find anything, leave the plant where it is.

Useful sites for checking the type of power plant:

- <http://globalenergyobservatory.org/list.php?db=PowerPlants&type=Gas> (you can search the power plant name or look for all plants in the country, it covers both oil and gas)

- https://www.gem.wiki/Main_Page (as above)

Step 6 - Refinery and Transmission & Distribution residual capacity

Copy and paste the residual capacity for the following technologies from the **residual capacity tab** of the TEMBA_21_10_Refer dataset into the **3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab** as below. If you see values of 0 for all years, you don't need to worry about copying that row in. If values are non-zero, copy the entire row in TEMBA from column B to BE:

- The row for XXCRUDRE1X in TEMBA (where XX is country code) should be copied to the Residual Capacity row for UPSREF001 in row 3181 in tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto), starting in column I
- The row for XXCRUDRE2X in TEMBA (where XX is country code) should be copied to the Residual Capacity row for UPSREF002 in row 3197 in tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto), starting in column I
- The row for XXELO0T00X in TEMBA (where XX is country code) should be copied to the Residual Capacity row for PWRTRN in row 1117 in tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto), starting in column I
- The row for XXELO0TDTX in TEMBA (where XX is country code) should be copied to the Residual Capacity row for PWRDIST in row 835 in tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto), starting in column I
- Note, the rows that you paste into should be the ones shaded in orange.

[we can probably automate this later but do it manually for now]

Make a note of the PWR technologies (rows 724-1197 in tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto)) that do not have any residual capacity in the country, we will use this in Step 7. Do not include the following technologies: PWRTRN, PWRDIST, PWRTRNIMP, PWRTRNEXP. Additionally, do this for the refinery technologies: UPSREF001 and UPSREF002 (rows 3166 to end) (XXCRUDRE1X & XXCRUDRE2X in TEMBA respectively).

Step 7 - Capacity Constraints

In the 3.8 Capacity & Inv Constraints tab, set the **Total Annual Max Capacity Investment** for 2015-2020 to 0 (column E to column J) for power generation and refinery technologies that have 0 residual capacity in the country, using the list you made in Step 7. Do not do this the following technologies: PWRTRN (row 439), PWRDIST (row 440), PWRTRNIMP (row 437), PWRTRNEXP (row 443).

Make sure the **Total Annual Max Capacity** is set to 0 for all years for offshore wind (PWRWND002, row 37) if this is infeasible in the country – if the country has no offshore wind potential, put 0 for the Total Annual Max Capacity for offshore wind all years (PWRWND002, row 37, 0 should be input from column E to BH).

Highlight the rows where you have added these constraints in green, so you remember to paste them to SAND later.

Step 8 - Demands

This is partly automated. Check that rows 7-11 in the 4. TEMBA Demands Data tab have been filled in with data (rows 7-11, columns C-BF). Make sure you are working in the **4. TEMBA Demands Data tab** (**not** the 4. TEMBA Demands Data (auto) tab).

For IEA countries: insert the final consumption (in PJ, convert from TJ if needed) for each fuel in each sector in the country for 2015-2018 into the table (rows 15-10, columns B to E) in the 4. TEMBA Demands Data tab from the IEA Sankey Diagram (<https://www.iea.org/sankey/#?c=World&s=Balance>), marking 0 if there is no consumption for that fuel/sector. Key points:

- For this step, ensure that you have selected the 'Final Consumption' option rather than 'Balance' in the navigation pane on the left of the IEA website
- Ensure you have changed the unit to PJ/TJ at the top of the diagram, and be sure to convert to PJ if it is in TJ (divide by 1000)
- You can see the consumption in each sector by clicking on the sector on the diagram, which opens a pie chart
- Change the year by dragging the slide along the bottom

For non-IEA countries:

- Find the UN Energy Balance for your country on the UN website [here](#) (there are pdfs for groups of countries in alphabetical order)
- For these countries we will only insert data in the 2018 and 2017 columns of the table in the 4. TEMBA demands data tab (columns D and E, rows 15-30). The UN energy balances are in TJ so be sure to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ when inserting data. The top section of the UN energy balance is usually marked as 2018, then 2017 data are below – but check this for your country.
- Look at the data in the 'Final energy consumption' sections of the energy balance for 2017 and 2018. For industry, use the values for 'Manufacturing, const, mining'. For transport use the values for 'Transport'. For commerce use the values 'Commerce and public services'. For residential use the values for 'Households'. Use 'All Oil' for oil products; sum the values for 'Primary biofuels/Waste' and 'Charcoal' for biofuels and waste.
- **Leave the columns for 2015 and 2016 (columns B and C) blank, then they won't be considered in the average calculated in column F.**

Demands will then be automatically calculated - check in the 4.1 Accumulated Annual Demand tab that the rows for TRAMCY, TRACAR, TRABUS, INDHEH, INDHEL, RESCKN, COMHEL, RESHEL have been filled in (shaded in green, between rows 19-29), and in the 4.2 Specified Annual Demand tab that the rows for INDELC, RESELC and COMELC (rows 22, 25 & 27) have been filled in (shaded in green).

Step 9 - Electricity demand profile

Copy and paste the hourly electricity demand profile for the country from the PLEXOS All Demand UTC 2015.tab dataset (in SharePoint [here](#)) into the 4.2 Elc Demand Profile Raw Data tab.

- In PLEXOS the countries are along the tab, with the region code (AF for Africa), followed by the country code), copy the whole column starting from row 2 to row 8761
- Paste the column into tab **4.2 Elc Demand Profile Raw Data** starting in cell B4 (marked in yellow)

Go to the **4.2 Specified Dem Profile Calc** tab and to the rows for RESELC, COMELC and INDELC (rows 21, 24 and 26). Adjust the value in column L (Bennet Factor), until the value in column M is exactly

equal to 1. Only small adjustments are needed e.g. if the value in column M is 1.007, first try adjusting the value in column L to 0.98 and see what happens, then make further small adjustments.

Check that Specified Demand Profiles have been calculated for RESELC, COMELEC and INDELC in the 4.2 Specified Demand Profile Output tab (columns W, Z, AB) - just check that these columns have been filled in.

Step 10 - Import & Export activity limits

For IEA countries: Insert the amounts of imported and exported electricity (PJ) from the IEA Sankey diagram (<https://www.iea.org/sankey/#?c=World&s=Balance>) for the country for 2015-2018 into the TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityUpperLimit rows for PWRTRNIMP (row 238) and PWRTRNEXP (row 244) in the tab 5.1 Activity in columns F (2015) to I (2018). Don't worry about columns beyond column I, where values are automatically calculated based on what you enter in columns F to I. Important points:

- For this Step ensure that you have selected the **'Energy Balance'** option in the left-hand navigation pane on the IEA Sankey website
- Ensure that the unit is set to PJ/TJ as in Step 8 and make sure to carry out unit conversions if needed
- You can also look for this data on IEA's energy balance tables
- If there is no data, set to 0.

For non-IEA countries: open the UN energy balance for the country that you used in the earlier demands step. Remember that the UN data are in TJ so you need to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ. Go to the tab 5.1 Activity. Insert the amounts of imported and exported electricity from the energy balance in 2017 and 2018 into the TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityUpperLimit rows for PWRTRNIMP (row 238) and PWRTRNEXP (row 244) in column H for 2017 and column I for 2018. Electricity imports and exports are found in the UN energy balance in the top section for each year in the rows for 'Imports' and 'Exports' under 'Electricity'. Don't worry about columns beyond column I, where values are automatically calculated based on what you enter in columns F to I. Important points:

- **Please also insert the values for 2017 into the columns for 2015 and 2016 (columns F and G) - we will assume imports & exports remain similar across years**
- **Don't include the minus sign found before the values for exports in the UN energy balance data**
- **Remember that the UN data are in TJ so you need to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ.**

Step 11 - Renewable and fossil resources

Insert the estimated renewable energy potentials in the country into the table in the tab Data in Brief Tables 8 & 9 from the sources indicated in the table below. I have made screenshots of the tables needed from each report to save you the time of going through the reports. Some notes:

- If the table does not contain a potential for geothermal, insert a value of 0 for the geothermal potential (geothermal potentials are only included in the report for Eastern/Southern Africa and can be assumed to be 0 elsewhere).
- If there is a dash in the report, assume 0.

- When using the World Small Hydropower Development Report tables, select the value from the far-right column titled “Potential (<10MW)”, or “Potential Capacity” for Middle Africa.
- When using the **IRENA SAPP and WAPP** reports for hydropower potential, the potential is sourced from the column titled ‘Identified Projects (MW)’ but also add the Existing Capacity (MW) as we want overall potential (instructions above tables in the links too). Ignore the small hydropower potentials in these reports as we are sourcing this from the report above. When using the **IRENA Eastern & Southern Africa report**, hydropower potential is taken from the column titled ‘Hydropower (MW), Potential’.

Country	Small Hydro	Hydro & Geothermal (where applicable)	PV, CSP, Wind
Angola, Botswana, DRC, Eswatini/Swaziland, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique Namibia, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe,	World Small Hydropower Development Report (tables here)	IRENA SAPP report (tables here)	Hermann et al. 2014 (tables here)
Benin, Burkina Faso, Cote D’Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo	World Small Hydropower Development Report (tables here)	IRENA WAPP report (tables here)	Hermann et al. 2014 (tables here)
Burundi, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Sudan, Uganda, Tanzania, Djibouti, Egypt, Libya	World Small Hydropower Development Report (tables here)	IRENA Eastern & Southern Africa report (tables here)	Hermann et al. 2014 (tables here)
Cameroon, C.A.R, Chad, Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Gabon, Mauritania, Somalia, Guinea-Bissau	World Small Hydropower Development Report (tables here) - note Chad & Eritrea are absent, assume 0.	TEMBA as before for now (table on pg 89 here). Hope to update with IRENA primary data if able to source CAPP & NAPP reports.	Hermann et al. 2014 (tables here)

Insert the estimated fossil fuel reserves in the country into the table in the tab Data in Brief Tables 8 & 9 from the table on page 88 of the TEMBA report ([here](#)). If there is a dash, assume 0. If the country is not in the table, this means we assume 0 domestic reserves so insert 0 for coal, gas and oil.

Check that total technology model period activity upper limits have been added for MINOIL, MINNGS and MINCOA in the 5.1 Activity tab (row 601, 605, 611), and that total annual max capacity limits have been updated for PWRGEO (row 24) and PWRHYD001-004 (rows 33, 34, 35) in the tab 3.8 Capacity & Inv Constraints if applicable.

3. Data preparation for Developing Asia

Step 1

Create a copy of the Asia Base Data Collection File (without opening the file) for your country in the same Data Preparation and Manipulation folder. Name the file: **New *countryname* Data Collection**. Open the file (in desktop app) and give it a little time. Click do not update links when the file loads.

Select the country in Tab 1. Model Initiation. Give it a little time to update everything.

Step 1.5 - Fuel costs

- Check if the country is a net importer/exporter/neutral for gas and coal and select the correct fuel prices from the [Asia data sheet](#)

Step 2 - Power transmission and distribution output activity ratios

- Use values from Asia data sheet which calculates OA ratios based on <https://www.indexmundi.com/facts/indicators/EG.ELC.LOSS.ZS/rankings/asia>, assuming combined losses reach 5% in 2050

Step 3 - PV, onshore & offshore wind and hydro capacity factors

This is automated apart from offshore wind. Check data for your country is inserted in the Raw PV/Onshore Wind/Hydro CFs tabs (not the (auto) tabs) and that output capacity factors for these technologies are in the output capacity factors tab. For offshore wind, take the average offshore capacity factor from the NREL Global Offshore Capacity Factor data (see [here](#)) and insert it into the 3.6 Capacity Factor Calculation tab for offshore wind (cells E36-L36).

Time zones are set up to calculate profiles for countries that are UTC +8, adjust this if the country is in a different timezone – change for PV and wind CFs and the demand profile

Step 4 - Off-grid capacity

Copy and paste the Cumulative/Additions Label for off-grid hydropower and off-grid solar PV for the country from the IRENA Installed Capacities data (in SharePoint Data Preparation & Manipulation folder [here](#)) into the Off-Grid Capacity tab. Note: if the IRENA file has the country but not the relevant off-grid technologies, assume the values are zero and you don't need to do anything.

- In the IRENA datasheet, ensure the 'Type' column (column AC) is filtered to '**off-grid**'
- Filter to your **country** in the 'IRENA Menu' column (column A)
- In the '**Sub-technology**' column, filter to Solar Photovoltaic
- Order by Years and then copy the 'Cumulative/Additions Label' column (column AL) into tab **3.7 Off-Grid Capacity**, cells C5-C24 – if there is no data for a year then put 0, ensure the years match up with the years in column A
- Repeat the process but filtering out for Renewable Hydropower as the sub-technology, copying the Cumulative/Additions Label column into cells B5-B24 in the tab 3.7 Off-Grid Capacity

Check that the residual capacity rows for PWR SOL002 and PWR HYD004 (rows 920 and 1085) are updated in the **3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab**.

Step 5 - On-grid residual capacity

This is automated. Check that on-grid residual capacity data for your country is in the 3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab. Focus on checking between rows 724-1197 as this is where the power plant technologies are (all begin with PWR).

The raw on-grid residual capacity data for your country can be found in a csv file [here](#) - check that there are no more than 11 power plants of each type in your country as this is the maximum number permitted by the spreadsheet. If there are more than 11 rows you can add extra rows manually and copy the extra data directly from the csv file.

A few manual adjustments are needed:

- For hydropower (rows 852-920), move any plants in the PWRHYD001 group to PWRHYD002 if they have capacity between 0.01-0.1GW, and to PWRHYD003 if less than 0.01GW (capacity is in column H). To move a plant, copy the entire row for that plant from column E to column AR and paste it in the corresponding cells for the technology group you are moving it to.
- For oil power plants (rows 985-1016), all residual capacity is automatically inserted as PWROHC001 (LFO plant), but you can do a quick Google search using the Power Plant name and move any plants to PWROHC002 (HFO gas turbine) using the method above if needed. If it is unclear or you can't find anything, leave the plant where it is.
- The same should be done for gas power plants (rows 921-952), moving plants from PWRNGS001 (CCGT) to PWRNGS002 (OCGT) if you can find out that the plant is an OCGT. If it is unclear or you can't find anything, leave the plant where it is.

Useful sites for checking the type of power plant:

- <http://globalenergyobservatory.org/list.php?db=PowerPlants&type=Gas> (you can search the power plant name or look for all plants in the country, it covers both oil and gas)
- https://www.gem.wiki/Main_Page (as above)

Step 6 - Refinery and Transmission & Distribution residual capacity

For now we will assume that the transmission and distribution residual capacity is equal to the total installed power generation capacity in GW from the res cap csv.

Make a note of the PWR technologies (rows 724-1197 in tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto)) that do not have any residual capacity in the country, we will use this in Step 7. Do not include the following technologies: PWRTRN, PWRDIST, PWRTRNIMP, PWRTRNEXP. Additionally, do this for the refinery technologies: UPSREF001 and UPSREF002 (rows 3166 to end) (XXCRUDRE1X & XXCRUDRE2X in TEMBA respectively).

Step 7 - Capacity Constraints

In the 3.8 Capacity & Inv Constraints tab, set the **Total Annual Max Capacity Investment** for 2015-2020 to 0 (column E to column J) for power generation and refinery technologies that have 0 residual capacity in the country, using the list you made in Step 7. Do not do this the following technologies: PWRTRN (row 439), PWRDIST (row 440), PWRTRNIMP (row 437), PWRTRNEXP (row 443).

Make sure the **Total Annual Max Capacity** is set to 0 for all years for offshore wind (PWRWND002, row 37) if this is infeasible in the country – if the country has no offshore wind potential, put 0 for the

Total Annual Max Capacity for offshore wind all years (PWRWND002, row 37, 0 should be input from column E to BH).

Highlight the rows where you have added these constraints in green, so you remember to paste them to SAND later.

Step 8 - Demands

Copy and paste the listed demands for your country into rows 3-6 in tab 4.1 Raw APEC & IEA Demand data from the APEC 7th Annual Energy Outlook datasheet (uploaded [here](#)).

For IEA countries: insert the final consumption (in PJ, convert from TJ if needed) for each fuel in each sector in the country for 2015-2018 into the table (rows 15-10, columns B to E) in the 4.1 Demand Data Manipulation tab from the IEA Sankey Diagram (<https://www.iea.org/sankey/#?c=World&s=Balance>), marking 0 if there is no consumption for that fuel/sector. Key points:

- For this step, ensure that you have selected the 'Final Consumption' option rather than 'Balance' in the navigation pane on the left of the IEA website
- Ensure you have changed the unit to PJ/TJ at the top of the diagram, and be sure to convert to PJ if it is in TJ (divide by 1000)
- You can see the consumption in each sector by clicking on the sector on the diagram, which opens a pie chart
- Change the year by dragging the slide along the bottom

For non-IEA countries:

- Find the UN Energy Balance for your country on the UN website [here](#) (there are pdfs for groups of countries in alphabetical order)
- For these countries we will only insert data in the 2018 and 2017 columns of the table in the 4.1 Demand Data Manipulation tab (columns D and E, rows 15-30). The UN energy balances are in TJ so be sure to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ when inserting data. The top section of the UN energy balance is usually marked as 2018, then 2017 data are below – but check this for your country.
- Look at the data in the 'Final energy consumption' sections of the energy balance for 2017 and 2018. For industry, use the values for 'Manufacturing, const, mining'. For transport use the values for 'Transport'. For commerce use the values 'Commerce and public services'. For residential use the values for 'Households'. Use 'All Oil' for oil products; sum the values for 'Primary biofuels/Waste' and 'Charcoal' for biofuels and waste.
- **Leave the columns for 2015 and 2016 (columns B and C) blank, then they won't be considered in the average calculated in column F.**

Demands will then be automatically calculated - check in the 4.1 Accumulated Annual Demand tab that the rows for TRAMCY, TRACAR, TRABUS, INDHEH, INDHEL, RESCKN, COMHEL, RESHEL have been filled in (shaded in green, between rows 19-29), and in the 4.2 Specified Annual Demand tab that the rows for INDELC, RESELC and COMELC (rows 22, 25 & 27) have been filled in (shaded in green).

Step 9 - Electricity demand profile

Copy and paste the hourly electricity demand profile for the country from the PLEXOS All Demand UTC 2015.tab dataset (in SharePoint [here](#)) into the 4.2 Elc Demand Profile Raw Data tab.

- In PLEXOS the countries are along the tab, with the region code (AF for Africa), followed by the country code), copy the whole column starting from row 2 to row 8761
- Paste the column into tab **4.2 Elc Demand Profile Raw Data** starting in cell B4 (marked in yellow)

Go to the **4.2 Specified Dem Profile Calc** tab and to the rows for RESELC, COMELC and INDEL (rows 21, 24 and 26). Adjust the value in column L (Bennet Factor), until the value in column M is exactly equal to 1. Only small adjustments are needed e.g. if the value in column M is 1.007, first try adjusting the value in column L to 0.98 and see what happens, then make further small adjustments.

Check that Specified Demand Profiles have been calculated for RESELC, COMELEC and INDEL in the 4.2 Specified Demand Profile Output tab (columns W, Z, AB) - just check that these columns have been filled in.

Step 10 - Import & Export activity limits

For IEA countries: Insert the amounts of imported and exported electricity (PJ) from the IEA Sankey diagram (<https://www.iea.org/sankey/#?c=World&s=Balance>) for the country for 2015-2018 into the TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityUpperLimit rows for PWRTRNIMP (row 238) and PWRTRNEXP (row 244) in the tab 5.1 Activity in columns F (2015) to I (2018). Don't worry about columns beyond column I, where values are automatically calculated based on what you enter in columns F to I. Important points:

- For this Step ensure that you have selected the **'Energy Balance'** option in the left-hand navigation pane on the IEA Sankey website
- Ensure that the unit is set to PJ/TJ as in Step 8 and make sure to carry out unit conversions if needed
- You can also look for this data on IEA's energy balance tables
- If there is no data, set to 0.

For non-IEA countries: open the UN energy balance for the country that you used in the earlier demands step. Remember that the UN data are in TJ so you need to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ. Go to the tab 5.1 Activity. Insert the amounts of imported and exported electricity from the energy balance in 2017 and 2018 into the TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityUpperLimit rows for PWRTRNIMP (row 238) and PWRTRNEXP (row 244) in column H for 2017 and column I for 2018. Electricity imports and exports are found in the UN energy balance in the top section for each year in the rows for 'Imports' and 'Exports' under 'Electricity'. Don't worry about columns beyond column I, where values are automatically calculated based on what you enter in columns F to I. Important points:

- **Please also insert the values for 2017 into the columns for 2015 and 2016 (columns F and G) - we will assume imports & exports remain similar across years**
- **Don't include the minus sign found before the values for exports in the UN energy balance data**
- **Remember that the UN data are in TJ so you need to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ.**

Step 11 - Renewable and fossil resources

Insert the estimated renewable energy potentials in the country into the table in the tab Data in Brief Tables 8 & 9 from the sources indicated in the table below. Some notes:

- Brunei: sources in table plus 70-80Mw hydro from <https://www.reeep.org/brunei-darussalam-2012>
- Indonesia: sources in table plus 41.426GW hydro (+450MW SHP if not in world shp report), 27.15GW geothermal from RBAP SE4ALL report (available at <https://www.asia-pacific.undp.org/content/rbap/en/home/library/climate-and-disaster-resilience/APRC-EE-2013-SE4ALL.html>)
- Papua New Guinea: 150MW wind, 4GW hydro (+5.7Mw SHP), 0.8GW geothermal from RBAP SE4ALL report
- Malaysia: sources below plus 0.49GW hydro from RBAP SEA4ALL report
- Myanmar: 40.4GW hydro and 4GW wind from <https://accept.aseanenergy.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/A-Review-of-RE-and-NDCs-in-ASEAN.pdf>
- Philippines: sources below plus 4GW geothermal and 10.5GW hydro from <https://accept.aseanenergy.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/A-Review-of-RE-and-NDCs-in-ASEAN.pdf>
- Thailand: sources below plus 4.542GW hydro (+50MW SHP) from RBAP SE4ALL report
- Vietnam: sources below plus 3.8GW hydro (+2.887GW small hydro) and 10GW pumped hydro and 0.4GW geothermal from RBAP SE4ALL report

Country	Small Hydro	PV and Wind	Solar Resource
Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam	World Small Hydropower Development Report	Exploring RE opportunities in select SE Asian countries 2019 report (use values in table at start with LCOE <\$150/MWh)	NREL datasets (see here)

If you are doing this for a new country, it is recommended to first check the sources in the table above for potentials and then fill any gaps with country-specific sources. The NREL wind capacity factor datasets (referenced [here](#)) can also be used to estimate wind resources.

Insert the estimated fossil fuel reserves in the country into the table in the tab Data in Brief Tables 8 & 9 from the table on page 88 of the TEMBA report ([here](#)). If there is a dash, assume 0. If the country is not in the table, this means we assume 0 domestic reserves so insert 0 for coal, gas and oil.

Check that total technology model period activity upper limits have been added for MINOIL, MINNGS and MINCOA in the 5.1 Activity tab (row 601, 605, 611), and that total annual max capacity limits have

been updated for PWRGEO (row 24) and PWRHYD001-004 (rows 33, 34, 35) in the tab 3.8 Capacity & Inv Constraints if applicable.

4. Data preparation for South America

Step 1

Create a copy of the Base Data Collection File (without opening the file) for your country in the same Data Preparation and Manipulation folder. Name the file: New countryname Data Collection. Open the file (in desktop app) and give it a little time. Click do not update links when the file loads.

Select the country in Tab 1. Model Initiation. Give it a little time to update everything.

Step 1b) Adjust for the Time Zone for PV, wind and specified demand.

Step 2 - Power transmission and distribution output activity ratios

Copy the output activity ratio rows for power transmission and distribution from the Data_Reference_SAMBA dataset (in the SharePoint Data Preparation & Manipulation folder [here](#)) to the rows in the 3.3 Output Activity Ratios tab. In SAMBA, in LossesTrans&Distr tab there is one table for transmission losses and one for distribution per each country.

In SAMBA LossesTrans&Distr tab, copy the entire row of your country from Column D to column BG and paste into row 41 of tab 3.3 Output Activity Ratios, starting in column F. For Brazil use the Brazil Average row 7.

In SAMBA LossesTrans&Distr tab, copy the entire row for your country from column D to column BG and paste into row 42 of tab 3.2 Output Activity Ratios, starting in column F. For Brazil use the Brazil Average row 24.

Step 3 - PV, onshore wind and hydro capacity factors

This is automated. Check data for your country is inserted in the Raw PV/Onshore Wind/Hydro/Offshore Wind CFs tabs (not the (auto) tabs) and that output capacity factors for these technologies are in the output capacity factors tab.

Offshore wind capacity factors will come from the NREL dataset. Copy and paste the average capacity factor (row L, cells 28-37, highlighted in green) for the country from [this spreadsheet](#) into the 3.6 Capacity Factor Calculation tab for PWRWND002 for every time slice.

Step 4 – Refinery Residual Capacity

Copy and paste the refinery capacity in kb/d from the [starter kits – list of countries](#) spreadsheet into the 3.7 Refinery ResCap tab. This will automatically be converted to the residual capacity output for UPSREF001. (The primary source for the refinery capacity is [McKinsey Latin American refineries](#)).

Step 5 - Off-grid capacity

If your country is covered by the IRENA Off-Grid data (Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, Paraguay, Uruguay, Venezuela): Copy and paste the Cumulative/Additions Label for off-grid hydropower and off-grid solar PV for the country from the IRENA Installed Capacities data (in SharePoint Data Preparation & Manipulation folder [here](#)) into the Off-Grid Capacity tab. Note: if the IRENA file has the country but not the relevant off-grid technologies, assume the values are zero and you don't need to do anything.

In the IRENA datasheet, ensure the 'Type' column (column AC) is filtered to 'off-grid'

Filter to your country in the 'IRENA Menu' column (column A)

In the 'Sub-technology' column, filter to Solar Photovoltaic

Order by Years and then copy the 'Cumulative/Additions Label' column (column AL) into tab 3.7 Off-Grid Capacity, cells C5-C24 – if there is no data for a year then put 0, ensure the years match up with the years in column A

Repeat the process but filtering out for Renewable Hydropower as the sub-technology, copying the Cumulative/Additions Label column into cells B5-B24 in the tab 3.7 Off-Grid Capacity

Check that the residual capacity rows for PWR SOL002 and PWR HYD004 (rows 920 and 1085) are updated in the 3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab.

If not in the IRENA list (Chile) -> **find a new source or make an assumption**

[we can probably automate this more later but do it manually for now]

Step 6 - On-grid residual capacity

This is automated. Check that on-grid residual capacity data for your country is in the 3.7 ResCap data (auto) tab. Focus on checking between rows 724-1197 as this is where the power plant technologies are (all begin with PWR).

The raw on-grid residual capacity data for your country can be found in a csv file [here](#) - check that there are no more than 11 power plants of each type in your country as this is the maximum number permitted by the spreadsheet. We are working on fixing this problem – for now just make a note if there are more than 11 and we will come back to it.

A few manual adjustments are needed:

For hydropower (rows 852-920), move any plants in the PWRHYD001 group to PWRHYD002 if they have capacity between 0.01-0.1GW, and to PWRHYD003 if less than 0.01GW (capacity is in column H). To move a plant, copy the entire row for that plant from column E to column AR and paste it in the corresponding cells for the technology group you are moving it to.

For oil power plants (rows 985-1016), all residual capacity is automatically inserted as PWROHC001 (LFO plant), but you can do a quick Google search using the Power Plant name and move any plants to PWROHC002 (HFO gas turbine) using the method above if needed. If it is unclear or you can't find anything, leave the plant where it is.

The same should be done for gas power plants (rows 921-952), moving plants from PWRNGS001 (CCGT) to PWRNGS002 (OCGT) if you can find out that the plant is an OCGT. If it is unclear or you can't find anything, leave the plant where it is.

Useful sites for checking the type of power plant:

<http://globalenergyobservatory.org/list.php?db=PowerPlants&type=Gas> (you can search the power plant name or look for all plants in the country, it covers both oil and gas)

https://www.gem.wiki/Main_Page (as above)

Step 7 – Cooking Residual Capacity

Insert the proportions of each fuel used for cooking (as a decimal) in the country from the country profile [here](#). This source gives estimates of the % of cooking done with each fuel. Count LPG and kerosene as oil. Cooking residual capacity will then be automatically estimated once the accumulated annual demand for RESCKN is filled in, and you can copy and paste the res cap rows for the stove technologies into SAND. If the country isn't in that source, just have a google and see if you can find anything to make an estimate from! Also, if the country seems to use electricity for the majority of its cooking, maybe make a note and we'll come back to it because I'm trying to work out how best to deal with that for some Asian countries.

Important note: TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityUpperLimit for DEMRESCKNBIO will be automatically calculated using the % of cooking that is done with biomass currently and the RESCKN demand for each year – make sure to copy this into SAND.

Step 8 - Transmission & Distribution residual capacity

For transmission and distribution, we will just make the crude assumption of residual capacity being equal to the installed on-grid residual power plant capacity:

Go to the res_cap CSV file for the country and work out the sum of all the capacities

Then insert this value for all years for PWRTRN and PWRDIST residual capacity

Make a note of the PWR technologies (rows 724-1197 in tab 3.7 ResCap data (auto)) that do not have any residual capacity in the country, we will use this in Step 7. Do not include the following technologies: PWRTRN, PWRDIST, PWRTRNIMP, PWRTRNEXP. Additionally, do this for the refinery technologies: UPSREF001 and UPSREF002 (rows 3166 to end).

Step 9 - Capacity Constraints

In the 3.8 Capacity & Inv Constraints tab, set the Total Annual Max Capacity Investment for 2015-2020 to 0 (column E to column J) for power generation and refinery technologies that have 0 residual capacity in the country, using the list you made in Step 7. Do not do this the following technologies: PWRTRN (row 439), PWRDIST (row 440), PWRTRNIMP (row 437), PWRTRNEXP (row 443).

Make sure the Total Annual Max Capacity is set to 0 for all years for offshore wind (PWRWND002, row 37) if this is infeasible in the country – if the country has no offshore wind potential, put 0 for the Total Annual Max Capacity for offshore wind all years (PWRWND002, row 37, 0 should be input from column E to BH).

Highlight the rows where you have added these constraints in green, so you remember to paste them to SAND later.

Step 10 - Demands

Regional demands taken from the [Energy Outlook of Latin America and the Caribbean 2019](#) and manipulated [here](#) from 2015 to 2070. Copy and paste the demands for each fuel in each country into the relevant row in the 4.1 Demands Data Manipulation tab.

For IEA countries: insert the final consumption (in PJ, convert from TJ if needed) for each fuel in each sector in the country for 2015-2018 into the table (rows 15-10, columns B to E) in the 4. TEMBA Demands Data tab from the IEA Sankey Diagram (<https://www.iea.org/sankey/#?c=World&s=Balance>), marking 0 if there is no consumption for that fuel/sector. Key points:

For this step, ensure that you have selected the 'Final Consumption' option rather than 'Balance' in the navigation pane on the left of the IEA website

Ensure you have changed the unit to PJ/TJ at the top of the diagram, and be sure to convert to PJ if it is in TJ (divide by 1000)

You can see the consumption in each sector by clicking on the sector on the diagram, which opens a pie chart

Change the year by dragging the slide along the bottom

Note:

You can also try to get this data from the IEA Energy Balance tables, but sometimes they aren't as up to date or detailed.

For non-IEA countries:

Find the UN Energy Balance for your country on the UN website [here](#) (there are pdfs for groups of countries in alphabetical order)

For these countries we will only insert data in the 2018 and 2017 columns of the table in the 4. TEMBA demands data tab (columns D and E, rows 15-30). The UN energy balances are in TJ so be sure to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ when inserting data. The top section of the UN energy balance is usually marked as 2018, then 2017 data are below – but check this for your country.

Look at the data in the 'Final energy consumption' sections of the energy balance for 2017 and 2018. For industry, use the values for 'Manufacturing, const, mining'. For transport use the values for 'Transport'. For commerce use the values 'Commerce and public services'. For residential use the values for 'Households'. Use 'All Oil' for oil products; sum the values for 'Primary biofuels/Waste' and 'Charcoal' for biofuels and waste.

Leave the columns for 2015 and 2016 (columns B and C) blank, then they won't be considered in the average calculated in column F.

Demands will then be automatically calculated - check in the 4.1 Accumulated Annual Demand tab that the rows for TRAMCY, TRACAR, TRABUS, INDHEH, INDHEL, RESCKN, COMHEL, RESHEL have been filled in (shaded in green, between rows 19-29), and in the 4.2 Specified Annual Demand tab that the rows for INDELC, RESELC and COMELC (rows 22, 25 & 27) have been filled in (shaded in green).

Step 11 - Electricity demand profile

Copy and paste the hourly electricity demand profile for the country from the PLEXOS All Demand UTC 2015.tab dataset (in SharePoint [here](#)) into the 4.2 Elc Demand Profile Raw Data tab.

In PLEXOS the countries are along the tab, with the region code (SA for South-America), followed by the country code), copy the whole column starting from row 2 to row 8761

Paste the column into tab 4.2 Elc Demand Profile Raw Data starting in cell B4 (marked in yellow)

[will hopefully be automated asap]

Go to the 4.2 Specified Dem Profile Calc tab and to the rows for RESELC, COMELC and INDELC (rows 21, 24 and 26). Adjust the value in column L (Bennet Factor), until the value in column M is exactly equal to 1. Only small adjustments are needed e.g. if the value in column M is 1.007, first try adjusting the value in column L to 0.98 and see what happens, then make further small adjustments.

Check that Specified Demand Profiles have been calculated for RESELC, COMELEC and INDELIC in the 4.2 Specified Demand Profile Output tab (columns W, Z, AB) - just check that these columns have been filled in.

Step 12 - Import & Export activity limits

For IEA countries: Insert the amounts of imported and exported electricity (PJ) from the IEA Sankey diagram (<https://www.iea.org/sankey/#?c=World&s=Balance>) for the country for 2015-2018 into the TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityUpperLimit rows for PWRTRNIMP (row 238) and PWRTRNEXP (row 244) in the tab 5.1 Activity in columns F (2015) to I (2018). Don't worry about columns beyond column I, where values are automatically calculated based on what you enter in columns F to I. Important points:

For this Step ensure that you have selected the 'Energy Balance' option in the left-hand navigation pane on the IEA Sankey website

Ensure that the unit is set to PJ/TJ as in Step 8 and make sure to carry out unit conversions if needed

You can also look for this data on IEA's energy balance tables

If there is no data, set to 0.

For non-IEA countries: open the UN energy balance for the country that you used in the earlier demands step. Remember that the UN data are in TJ so you need to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ. Go to the tab 5.1 Activity. Insert the amounts of imported and exported electricity from the energy balance in 2017 and 2018 into the TotalTechnologyAnnualActivityUpperLimit rows for PWRTRNIMP (row 238) and PWRTRNEXP (row 244) in column H for 2017 and column I for 2018. Electricity imports and exports are found in the UN energy balance in the top section for each year in the rows for 'Imports' and 'Exports' under 'Electricity'. Don't worry about columns beyond column I, where values are automatically calculated based on what you enter in columns F to I. Important points:

Please also insert the values for 2017 into the columns for 2015 and 2016 (columns F and G) - we will assume imports & exports remain similar across years

Don't include the minus sign found before the values for exports in the UN energy balance data

Remember that the UN data are in TJ so you need to divide by 1000 to convert to PJ.

Step 13 - Renewable and fossil resources

Insert the estimated renewable energy potentials in the country into the table in the tab Data in Brief Tables 8 & 9 from the sources indicated in the table below. I have made screenshots of the tables needed from each report to save you the time of going through the reports.

Country	Small Hydro	Hydro & Geothermal (where applicable)	PV, CSP, Wind
Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, French Guiana, Guyana, Paraguay, Peru, Suriname,	World Small Hydropower Development Report (tables here)	Data_Reference_S AMBA (screenshot of useful table here) - subtract the data for small hydropower potential	Solar resource from this NREL dataset . Copy and paste the 'Total' value (column J) from the Solar Resource tab here into the 'Solar Resource' row in the table. From the same spreadsheet, copy and paste the offshore and onshore wind potentials in TWh/yr into the

Uruguay, Venezuela			relevant row in the table. (Wind potential from this NREL dataset .)
-----------------------	--	--	--

Important note: total technology annual activity upper limit for PWRWND002 will be automatically calculated based on the potential you just added to the table – make sure to add that to SAND

Insert the estimated fossil fuel reserves in the country into the table in the tab Data in Brief Tables 8 & 9 from the table from Data_Reference_SAMBA report ([here](#)). If there is a dash, assume 0. If the country is not in the table, this means we assume 0 domestic reserves so insert 0 for coal and oil.

Coal -> Coal for Electricity Tab; Oil -> HF for Electricity

For natural gas reserves data were taken from [BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2019 | 68th edition](#).

Check that total technology model period activity upper limits have been added for MINOIL, MINNGS and MINCOA in the 5.1 Activity tab (row 601, 605, 611), and that total annual max capacity limits have been updated for PWRGEO (row 24) and PWRHYD001-004 (rows 33, 34, 35) in the tab 3.8 Capacity & Inv Constraints if applicable.

5. Model & Scenario Creation

Step 1 – Data Prep File -> SAND Interface

Step 2 – Creating Scenarios & Running the Model

Scenario Input Data and Fossil Future - [Video 1](#), [Video 2](#)

1. Create a copy of the 'Scenario Constraints' file ([here](#)) and name it 'Country Scenario Constraints'
2. Follow the instructions in the 'Input Data' tab of your Country Scenario Constraints file to add a few bits of data for the country
3. You can then close your Data Collection file (which should make your laptop happier)
4. Go to the Fossil Future tab in the Country Scenario Constraints file and follow the instructions there to set up the Fossil Future scenario in a copy of your Base SAND file named Country FF SAND (all instructions needed should be in this tab). Then download the Country FF SAND file to your local computer – I suggest creating a folder called 'Runs' on your Desktop and putting this (and everything else from now on) in here.
5. Download the OSeMOSYS code version we are using ([here](#)) and place it in the same folder.
6. You can then run the Fossil Future scenario (just as you did in the Hands On Exercises, instructions [here](#) for reference - starting from page 13 'Run the model' - note that you should select the OSeMOSYS code that you just downloaded)
7. Download a copy of the Results Database file ([here](#)) to your computer in the same folder as above
8. Create a copy of the Results Database named Country FF Results Database
9. IMPORTANT: rename the results file produced by clicSAND to remove the spaces (see video)
10. Import the Country FF Results to this database as done in the Hands On Exercise (instructions also [here](#), from the bottom of page 15 where it says 'Results Visualisation' - follow these steps

when you open your Country FF Results Database, using the file path for your Country FF Results txt file)

11. Download a copy of the Results Template ([here](#)) to your computer and put it in the same folder as above.
12. Create a copy of the Results Template you downloaded called Country FF Results, then open this file and change the source for each of the pre-made pivot tables to the Country FF Results Database that you just made (as done [here](#) on page 19).
13. Be sure to check all relevant technologies are selected using the filters in the pivot tables – I have added notes to the Results Template saying which should be selected for each graph (also see video). Check that none of the BSTOP technologies are producing/have capacity in any of the pivot tables/charts.

Least Cost - [Video 1](#), [Video 2](#) (same method as in FF Video 2, just for reference)

14. Go back to the Country Scenario Constraints file and follow the instructions to set up the Least Cost scenario in the Least Cost tab.
15. Once set up, download the Country LCv1 SAND file and run it as done for the FF scenario. Repeat the process above to set up the results database and results excel file for LCv1 – creating a copy of the results database and results template you downloaded and naming them Country LCv1 Results Database/Results. Remember to change the file name of the results file produced by clicSAND to remove the spaces before importing to the database and to select all the relevant technologies for each graph in the Results Excel file.
16. Then go back to the Country Scenario Constraints file and follow the instructions to set up Country LCv2, before running it and creating the results files in the same way.

Net Zero - [Video](#)

17. Go back to the Country Scenario Constraints file and follow the instructions to set up the Net Zero scenario in the Net Zero tab.
18. Once set up, download the Country NZv1 SAND file and run it as done for the FF and LC scenarios. Repeat the process above to set up the results database and results excel file for NZv1.
19. Then go back to the Country Scenario Constraints file and follow the instructions to set up Country NZv2, before running it and creating the results files in the same way. --> Net Zero Done.
20. Upload the Results excel files, data txt files and results txt files for FF, LCv2 and NZv2 in the relevant folder [here](#).

Method of running without clicSAND

See this [short video](#).

Command to generate the lp file from the command window (replace the file paths with your own):

```
Command Prompt
C:\Users\lalli>glpsol -m C:\Users\lalli\Desktop\Runs\osemosys_starterkit.txt -d C:\Users\lalli\Desktop\Runs\BurkinFasoFF.txt --wlp C:\Users\lalli\Desktop\Runs\BurkinFasoFFinput.lp --check
```

Command to solve in cbc:

```
C:\Cbc-2.7.5-win64-intel11.1\Cbc-2.7.5-win64-intel11.1\bin\cbc.exe
Welcome to the CBC MILP Solver
Version: 2.7.5
Build Date: Nov 10 2011
Revision Number: 1759

CbcSolver takes input from arguments ( - switches to stdin)
Enter ? for list of commands or help
Cbc:import C:\Users\lalli\Desktop\Runs\BurkinaFasoNZv2input.lp
Cbc:ratio 0.05 solve_
```

6. Generation of Article & Figures

The figures and data article are generating using scripts available on the CCG Github [here](#). (The repository is private so please ask Will Usher/Karla Cervantes Barron for access to the Starter Kits repository. There is one script for each region, containing the appropriate text and layout for that region. You should download the script for the correct region and then edit the file paths, replacing them with the corresponding file path on your PC – there are many file paths, so please make sure that you change them all. Also ensure that you ‘sync local files’ in the Share Point Starter Kits folder so that they are on your PC.

You can indicate which country or countries you want to create articles for in the script around line 143. If you want to run multiple countries, you should leave these lines as in the screenshot below and add a column to the [Starter Kits – List of Countries](#), putting a 1 for countries that you want to include, and a 0 if you don’t want to include them. You should then add the name of that column in the square brackets after Country_Data in lines 143 and 144 (where it says Run_SA in the screenshot). If you want to only run one country, you should # out lines 143 and 144, then remove the # from lines 146 and 147 and insert the country name and ISO3 code.

```
139
140 # In[349]:
141
142
143 countries_short = country_data[country_data['Run_SA']==1]['Country']
144 icountries = country_data[country_data['Run_SA']==1]['ISO3']
145
146 #countries_short = ["Cambodia"]
147 #icountries = ['KHM']
148
```

In the Starter Kits – List of Countries, make sure that you have indicated the domestic refinery capacity (from the McKinsey Refinery Reference Desk) in tb/d in column S. The author list and affiliations should also be added in columns L and M. You should also indicate the reference list to be used in column U. Reference lists should be named ‘Reference List – Name’ and stored in [this folder](#), with the Name portion written in column U of the Starter Kits – List of Countries. Be sure not to activate URLs in your reference list, otherwise the script cannot pick them up. Ensure that you have the reference list downloaded onto your computer and that you update the file path in line 373 of the script (see below).

```

367
368     # loop iso and country
369     # for ic, country in zip(icountries, countries_short):
370
371     # Variable Reference Imports
372     refl = country_data[country_data['Country']==country]['Reference List'].values[0]
373     input_doc = Document(r'C:/Users/lalli/Desktop/CCG/Reference List {}.docx'.format(refl)
374     # output_doc = Document(r'C:/Users/KarlaC/CCG_Starter_Kits/outputs/{0}/DiB_{1}.docx'.fi
375
376     document = Document()

```

Before running the script, make sure that the following files are uploaded for the country/countries that you are trying to run:

- New *Country Data Collection* in [this folder](#)
- Country FF Results, Country LCv2 Results, Country NZv2 Results – Excel results files moved to [this CHECKED folder](#) once you are happy with them and ready to run. Even if you are not including Net Zero in the article, you should upload a ‘dummy’ excel results file with the same name and then delete the figures from the article afterwards.

You should then be ready to run the script and create the articles. You should see figures created in a ‘figures’ folder and articles in an ‘outputs’ folder, both in the file path you specified in the script.

Once the articles are ready, there are a few manual things to do – listed [here](#) - these can be done by an internal reviewer. You should also check that the references are correct e.g. if you used a country-specific unique source but a generic regional reference list you would need to make an adjustment.

7. Creation of Zenodo Repository

The zenodo repository can be created with [this script](#) that is part of the CCG Github, which contains the following instructions for use:

1. Get a *Personal access token* at <https://zenodo.org/account/settings/applications/>. The `deposit:write` is enough: to be on the safe side, the script does not publish the uploaded papers, the *Publish* button has to be pushed manually. (Once a document is published on Zenodo, the attached files cannot be modified.)
2. Paste your personal token into a file called `.token` and place in your working directory (or paste into `run.bat` file)
3. Place `Starter Kit - List of Countries.xlsx` in the root folder
4. Place `authors.xlsx` in the root folder
5. Place subfolders of csv files in the `data` folder. Subfolder names should match country names in `Starter Kit - List of Countries.xlsx`
6. You may wish to update certain fields in `data/template.txt` such as publication date. This is used as a template for each of the metadata files generated in the next step.
7. Run `run.sh` (Linux or OSX) or `run.bat` (Windows). This scripts should first create a file `data/data.csv` which contains all of the countries info. Then, individual `<country>.json` Zenodo metadata files are created. Finally, the folders are uploaded to Zenodo.

Customising the uploads

1. Create a template JSON describing your submissions. Check the [documentation](#) (Representations > Deposition metadata) for details about it.
 - Use `{key-name}` for parts that are different for each submission.
 - An example template and some example deposition metadata files can be found in the example folder.
 - The JSON description of any submitted document can be checked by clicking on the JSON link in the Export panel (or by checking the `https://zenodo.org/record/{ID}/export/json` URL.)
2. Create a CSV file that describes the parts that are different for each submission.
 - The `{key-name}` strings of the template will be replaced by the values from the column having `key-name` as header in the CSV file.
 - The CSV file should contain a `FILENAME` column, describing the name of the file created by substituting the values from the given row to the template.
3. Place the CSV datafile and template into the `data` folder.
4. Execute the script `fill_template.py` to generate the descriptors (deposition metadata) for each submission.
 - Usage: `fill_template.py <template_filename> <data_filename>`, where `<template_filename>` is the name (path) of the template file, and `<data_filename>` is the name (path) of the CSV data file.
5. Place subfolders of CSV files into the `data` folder
6. Execute the script `upload_to_zenodo.py` to upload your submissions.
 - Usage: `upload_to_zenodo.py <token> <directory>`, where `<token>` is your personal access token, and `<directory>` is the directory that contains the JSON and PDF files to be uploaded.
7. Go to the [Upload page](#), check and publish your submissions.

To run the script, the user must first clone this repository to a local file (either by using the command 'git clone' or by downloading the zip file directly from Github and saving it into a desired folder). Then, the user can use either the command line or Anaconda prompt to run the script. IMPORTANT: Open the folder containing the run.bat script before running it, otherwise it gives an error. This can be done with the typical command 'cd folder1/folder2'.

Apart from the instructions presented there, if the user is using the Anaconda prompt, then the instruction for running the batch script (run.bat) should be done by using the command 'call run.bat'.

Common errors encountered while running the script have been 1) spaces found in the list of authors names or surnames, in which case the spaces must be removed in the Excel file; 2) having a folder with the figures inside the country folders, in which case any folder within the country folder must be removed, since the script won't be able to deal with it.

After running the script, you should log in to Zenodo and check that the uploads are there. They will not be published yet: before clicking publish you should delete any additional files that you don't want to upload, e.g. the DiB article, so that you only publish the csv files, readme, and base SAND file. Once ready you need to click save, then publish.

8. Upload of Pre-Print Articles

Articles for the first set of starter kits were uploaded on Research Square. When uploading to Research Square, we slightly modified the article to better suit their formatting. Create a copy of the DiB article and make the following adjustments:

- Rename Figure A3 as Figure 1 and then adjust numbering of other figures
- Then adjust the text and first table to account for the changes in figure titles

When uploading to Research Square, you should upload the DiB word file, along with the figures from the main article in separate image files (figure A3 which is now named figure 1, plus the graphs for RE costs, fuel prices, and demand projection). The figures can be found in the 'figures' folder created when you ran the script to generate the article. Also upload the data txt files for the scenarios included in the appendix as supplementary files. The category should be Energy Engineering and the article type is Data Note.

9. Future Uptake of Starter Kits

Some ideas for those wanting to use and build on the starter kits are detailed below. Works using the starter kits should always cite the pre-print paper and Zenodo repository.

Modifying the Input Data

- Currently the same demand profile is used across all sectors – it probably wouldn't be too difficult to adjust this for each sector to account for peaks occurring at different times etc.
- Currently we use generic data for the costs of cooking, transport and heating technologies – it would definitely add value if you could find more country- or region-specific costs
- We only consider CO₂ emissions – adding in emissions factors for methane or other GHGs would be an improvement
- Residual capacity is based on a global power model (PLEXOS) and IRENA off-grid capacity data – these sources will certainly have gaps so it would be good to compare the data to those from the government data or other in-country sources. Planned projects should also be added.

Modifying Model Structure

- It would be beneficial to further split demands within sectors and potentially add others such as agriculture (as being done for Zambia)
- Demands are treated very simply – it would be valuable to improve these, for example by converting the transport demand to consider final transport demand in vehicle km. On the note of transport, a wider range of transport technologies could be added and you could source country-specific data on modal share (currently an assumption is made for each country based on regional data)
- There is a uniform approach to time-slicing with 4 seasons used, each split into day and night. It would certainly improve accuracy if you were to increase the accuracy of time representation to consider the seasonality in the country. This would require you to adjust the capacity factor and specified demand profiles, and potentially the year split depending on your approach
- Currently only 1 region is used – perhaps for countries with significant geographic variability you could employ a multi-region approach to improve accuracy
- Storage and flexibility are considered very simply. You could add specific storage technologies to the model to improve this
- Other technologies could be added (and potentially could be added to starter kits in v2): interconnector projects (existing and planned); LNG terminals

Modifying Assumptions

- In the scenarios there are gradual investment constraints on demand-side technologies and renewable energy potentials are considered. However, you could use in-country knowledge to limit yearly investment in power plant technologies to make capacity expansion more realistic. It would probably be equally as important to improve the consideration of the time taken to approve and construct each power plant technology, probably using total annual max capacity investment in OSeMOSYS
- Imports and exports are modelled very simply. It is simply assumed that the country can continue to import and export power at the same levels as in 2020, with no costs considered. To improve you could allow imports and exports to scale with demand and add an electricity price to allow the model to import and export as is economic. Interconnectors are also not considered (possibly to be added in version 2)
- It would be good to improve the consideration of the country's policies and plans, e.g. the model currently allows investment in any technologies that are technically feasible in the country (although nuclear is turned off in all scenarios), but it may be that certain technologies are more or less likely to feature in the country due to policy goals, conflicts with land and water use etc.

10. Potential Improvements for Future Iterations

Some ideas and key things flagged to potentially improve/add in version 2 of the starter kits:

- More data an oil and gas sector
- Improved consideration of demands to consider demand for services/useful energy e.g. transport demand in vkm etc.
- Add agricultural sector
- Consider construction/lead times of power plants more
- Add interconnector projects